

PROBLEMS OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF COMBINATIONS OF HIGHLY QUALIFIED HANDBALL PLAYERS IN COMPETITIVE CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the general concept of Handball, the history of handball, the structure of the game, the problems that occur in the game and how to approach them correctly.

Team handball was invented in Europe around the 1890's. The game that we know today originated in Germany at the end of the nineteenth century, when it was introduced to the world by a gymnastics master, Konard Koch. However, the development of the game since its introduction has not been some first it was not have its own governing body it came under the international Amateur athletic federation. It was played in outdoor with 11 players per team. Team Handball Modern handball was first played towards to end of 19th century the real impulses emanated from Denmark, Germany and Sweden. In 1928, eleven handball playing nations met in Amsterdam on the occasion of the Olympic Games and as a result of this meeting, the international amateur handball federation was formed. In 1935, just three years often attaining a separate entity, handball was included in the program of the games by the international

Olympic committee. This game was first included in the Olympics held in Berlin in 1936 and Indoor handball was invented in the 1940s in Denmark with 7 players per team. Holger Neilson. An international handball match for the first time was played in Germany it was highly popular among other countries after some years the participant countries develop a head them Germany in the Olympic game for example : Yugoslavia, Rumania , Russia, Bulgaria Poland, Hungary etc are highly popular in the world. The indoor game is now the more popular in the whole world. Handball History The origins of handball are not clearly known. One opinion says that the game was invented in Germany in the late 19th century, as an outdoor sport to keep soccer players fit during the summer months. However, there are evidences that suggest that a sport very similar to handball was played in ancient times as well. However, the first match of the modern era

was officially recorded on the 29th of October 1917 in Berlin, Germany. In 1906 a Danish gym teacher, lieutenant and Olympic medalist Holger Nielsen from Ordrup grammar school north of Copenhagen published the first set of team handball rules. However the modern set of rules was devised by Max Heiser, Kari Schelenz, and Erich Kc-nigh of Germany and was published on the 29th of October 1917. After 1919 Karl Schelenz improved these rules. A committee was nominated in 1926, by the Congress of the International Amateur Athletics Federation to frame international rules for field handball. In 1928, the International Amateur Handball Federation was formed. 18 years later, in 1946, the International Handball Federation was constituted.

Principles of training According to Rainer martens (N.G)and Dietrich Harre. Follow these 8 cardinal training principles helping to designing effective fitness program.

1. Principle of specificity suggests that your body will make adjustments according to the type of training you perform and in the very same muscles that you exercise. How you train determines what you get. This principle guides you in designing your fitness training program. If your goal is to improve your overall level of fitness, you would devise a wellrounded build program that builds both endurance and overall body strength. if you want to build the size of your biceps, you would increase weight loads on bicep curls and related exercises. Goldberg .
2. The Principle of Overload, implies that you must continually increase training loads as your body adapts over time. Because your body builds and adjusts of your existing training regimen, you must gradually and systematically increase your work load for continued improvement. A

generally accepted guideline for weight training is to increase resistance not more than 10% per week. You can also use percentages of your maximum or estimated maximum level of performance and work out within a target training zone of about 60-85% of maximum. As your maximum performance improves, your (raining loads will increase, as well.

3. The Principle of Recovery assets that you must get adequate rest between workouts in order to recuperate. How much rest you need depends upon your training program, level of fitness, diet, and other factors. Generally, if you perform a total body weight workout three days per week, rest at least 48 hours between sessions. you can perform cardio more frequently and on successive days of the wee.

4. The Principle of Reversibility refers to the loss of fitness that results after you stop training. In time, you will revert back to your pre-training condition. The biological principle of use and disuse underlies this principle. Simply stated. If you don't use it.yon lose it. While adequate recovery time is essential, taking long breaks results in detraining effects that may be noticeable within a few weeks. Significant levels of fitness are lost over longer periods. Only about 10% of strength is lost 8 weeks after training stops, but 30-40% of endurance is lost in the same time period. The Principle of Reversibility does not apply to skills. The effects of stopping practice of" motor skills, such as weight training exercises and sport skills, arc very different. Coordination appears to store in long-term motor memory and remains nearly perfect for decades. A- Skill once learned is never forgotten. Jensen and fisher.

5. The Principle of Variation implies that you should consistently change aspects of your workouts. Training variations should always occur within ranges that are aligned with your training directions and goals. Varying exercises, sets, reps, intensity, volume, and duration, for example, prevents boredom and promotes more consistent improvement over time.

6. The principle of Transfer suggests that workout activities can improve the performance of other skills with common elements, such as sport skills, work tasks, or other exercise. For example, performing explosive squats can improve the vertical jump due to their common movement qualities. But dead lifting would not transfer well to marathon swimming due to their very dissimilar movement qualities.

7. The Principle of individualization suggests that fitness training programs should be-adjusted for personal differences, such as abilities, skills, gender experience, motivation, past injuries, and physical condition. While general principles and best practices are good guides, each person's unique qualities must be part of the exercise equation. There is no one size full all training program.

8. The Principle of Balance is a broad concept that operates at different levels of healthy living. It suggests that you must maintain the right mix of exercise, diet, and healthy-behaviors. Falling out of balance may cause a variety of conditions (e.g., anemia, obesity) that affect health and fitness. In short, it suggests all things in moderation, For fitness training, balance also applies to muscles. If opposing muscles (e.g., hamstrings and quadriceps in the upper legs) are not strengthened in the right proportions, injuries can result. Muscle

imbalances also contribute to tendinitis and postural deviations.

Developing a plan for motivating your athletes and your teams.

1) Get input from your athletes (and most importantly your leaders) - check with your athletes to determine if what you are communicating to them is understood, what they need, and what they want. Encourage your leaders to make suggestions as to how things (e.g., practices, travel, game day preparations, etc.) might be improved. Remember; if you are asking for input... at least be willing to incorporate something (a suggestion) at some point.

2) Keep your athletes informed as to when, where, how, and why (and WHY is most important) - people are not generally motivated to start (or finish) a task that is not clear in terms of when, where, how, or why. Take away any questions or doubts that your athletes may have by clearly and consistently communicating your expectations and intentions. Be clear as to when, where, and how . . . but most important, be sure your athletes know "why" they are being asked to do something.

3) Create an environment that allows for Challenge, recognition, appreciation and quality - some of your athletes will be motivated by a challenge, some by recognition, some by appreciation, and some by quality of performance. It is important to know your athletes and what their primary motive might be. Challenge some (1 v 1 against a teammate), recognize others in front of their teammates (at the end of practice or in the locker room), appreciate others in private (in your office or the hallway), and provide others with a chance to show you a quality performance (quality over quantity of work). Remember,

different athletes are motivated by different situations and feedback.

4) Give your athletes a reason to want to work hard - take the time to develop genuine, honest, caring, and trusting relationships with your players. Athletes will work harder (and longer) for someone they know genuinely believes in 24 them, cares about them, and is committed to helping them achieve their potential.

At the heart of player motivation . . . is the quality of the coach-athlete relationship

5) Model what you want to see - be motivated yourself. If you want someone to work hard, you better be working hard. If you want someone to put in extra time, you better be putting in extra time. Athletes do what they see. This is why the motivation of the coaching staff is so important and why it is so important to have quality team leaders who can lead by example, hold accountable, and promote a climate of motivation and inspiration. Set a motivational "standard" by what you do, say, and expect. Say it, expect it, but also make sure you do it!

Luck of Proper Facilities. Physical education learning experience becomes more memorable through the proper use of supplementary demonstration aid each coach should have a variety of good instructional materials but should remember that the more exposure to learning. All such materials should assist players to learn and should not be used as a means of entertainment where properly used such aids can increase the depth and speed of their Technique and skills. In regard to the above concepts Home noted that "the physical education program needs demand of mind the quality and quantity of needs dictate the quality and quantity of facilities needed" According Jesse and Williams in some Sport project the shortage

of facilities are very real. They also emphatically explain that there remain many Sport Project and institutions with the most limited facilities On the influence that shortage of facilities can play claim they further suggests, when facilities are lacking or mearge as in innumerable schools then class in physical education are held in classrooms corridors and basements. Such places limit the program and when facilities are lacking children do not learn the skill and coordination that is essential for their development. When handball fell shortage of the facilities required teachers will also be in a problem on this issue they write it follows inevitably that luck of facilities has its effect up on the moral of teachers as well as on the teaching learning process the problems can in part be tackled if the necessary materials are available. On this issue Perstarises and Sinclair wrote "a high priority must be assigned to facilities that can meet the challenges since overcoming obstacles means creating a better situations without the help of facilities the realization of the objective of physical education seems impossible on this regard.

Phases of team development. A team is a living and dynamic entity. It could progress from an early to a mature phase, independent of the nature of the team or the task it must perform . Tuchman's model proposed the following typical phases in team development :

1) Forming : this is the initial orientation period. The team is unsure about what it is supposed to do; members do not know each other well or are not yet familiar with the way the team leader and the other members function. This stage is complete when the members begin to see themselves as a part of the group.

II) Storming: During this stage members begin to find their place as team members. The team members now feel more comfortable giving their opinion and challenging the team leader's authority and recommendations. Some members may become dissatisfied and challenge not only the tasks of the team and how these will be carried out, but also the leader's role and style of leadership. This is the start of intra-group conflicts.

III) Norming: in this team members begin to use their past experiences to solve their problems and pull together as a cohesive group. This process should result in the

team establishing procedures for handling conflicts, decisions, and methods to accomplish the team projects.

IV) Performing: In this stage the team working effectively and efficiently toward achieving its goals. Leadership is provided by the team members best suited for the task at hand. Members have learned how to work together, manage conflict and contribute their resources to meet the team's purposes.

V) Dissolving or Reorientation: the team dissolves when the team has completed the project. It may be reoriented to continue on a next phase of the project.

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